

ABDULLA QAHHOR IS A MASTER OF WORDS

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Abstract. Abdulla Qahhor's skill in using words. Methodology and objectives of vocabulary skills. There will be a discussion about Nasir's fine art in the use of words.

Keywords: Thorough thought, sharp sarcasm, great brevity, keeping up with the times, perfect image, deep discussion.

INTRODUCTION

Abdulla Qahhor is the leading representative of 20th century Uzbek prose. Zaki's prose works are distinguished by their brevity, modernity, thorough thinking, humor and satire, which cannot be found in the works of other prose writers. At the same time, the writer responds to the changes of his time with deep discussions.

MAIN PART

A. Qahhor shows the infinite power of words in every work. For example: in the fairy tale "Bribery" there is such a sentence: "It didn't work, the pain got worse and worse, not even water could pass through his throat, but he was covered with cotton in his mouth - crushed water came from his nose"¹. The description of "Tomi - crushed water" in the above sentence is a whole picture. Nasir does not think that the word "dripping" water is inappropriate to the sentence and creates a perfect image in the reader's mind by saying "Tomi - crushed water". There are many skills in using such words in the works. They bring out different styles and goals and perform tasks. Some of them show a lot more height in the critical stories that are typical of A. Qahhor's work. These are the stories "Speech" and "Artist" which were created with a clear word criterion. In the story "Artist", the artist's language culture and at the same time his level are taken into account, and it begins with the objection of the tractor driver to the artist. At least learn what to say, say the words correctly! I don't know what, what is not right? Until now, reporters and writers have not criticized me; I went through formalism and naturalism - no one gave me an answer. No one even took me in the place of giving birth. Now a tractor driver criticizes!..". The tractor driver blames the artist for mispronouncing one of the lines of the song. The artist sings the phrase "If I can kiss your lips, I'll be sugarless", "If I can kiss your lips, I'll be sugarless". When you read this sentence, you will clearly feel the

¹ "Tales from the past" stories and stories, NEW CENTURY GENERATION 2019.

vocabulary and level of speech of the hero. This story is also important for its hidden meaning. It is said above from the language of the artist: "No one even took me in the place of Otvod². Now a tractor driver is criticizing!.." pay attention to the phrase used in the sentence. The artist thinks about it in the form of "He could not put it in his mouth" and not in the form of "He could not put it into his mouth". This situation alone makes it clear that Abdulla Qahhor is a master of words, a real genius in the image of words, because not to mention means not to say a word about a person, not to remember that person, and not to mention abstinence from something is widely used in the sense of not eating or drinking at all. With the use of this expression, the writer, who deeply understands the nuances of the phrase, once again reveals the common language literacy of the artist.

In the writer's story "Bright Peaks", the life of young sisters is mentioned, that is, the story of Fatima and Zuhra's step into big life. In it, Zuhra runs away with a stranger, and Zuhra, who was brought up as a "superstitious" child of the Soviet state, sends home the following letter: flowing in the arms of marriage, we are going towards the bright peaks of the future. You have lived in the painful embrace of feudalism, you do not know what love based on high ideals is, so do not be sad about me, your happy days are coming". If you pay attention to the sentence at the end of the letter, "The days of your happiness are approaching", it will bring the thoughts of the parents to the thousand and one streets of the imagination, as well as make the reader think. What is the day when they will be happy? Is it the fruit of opening the way for her to study even more than Fatima, the day when an educated girl returns to her mother's arms? But Zuhra did not do that. He stepped over the threshold of his house and made a mistake. Abdulla Qahhor writes down the characters and words of the characters in each of his works. He finds and uses words and phrases that match their spirit. This makes the story a whole story. As the writer feels the power of the word and uses its magic in his stories, the various possibilities of the Uzbek language rise again among people. None of the words are just words, each of them conveys meaning without being used for pathos. If we take the word system of the story "Speech" as an example, then the writer created a vivid story about the consequences of improper use of words and style. Every sentence in it makes a person laugh and enjoy reading the story. Nowhere in Abdulla Qahhor's stories does the weight of words exceed the plot of the story, and it does not flow out of the mold or cause difficulty in understanding it. All of them form a whole, so that you cannot say

² www.ziyonet.uz

that removing one word will make the story complete. An example of this is the beginning of the story "The Patient", which is small in size. "Sotiboldi's wife fell ill".

CONCLUSION

As the story begins with this sentence, the next sentences are skillfully placed on top of it. If you want to replace the above sentence with another sentence, it will not meet the requirements of the following sentences. This is another evidence that the writer is definitely a skilled artist of words.

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1. "Tales from the past" stories and stories, NEW CENTURY GENERATION 2019.
2. www.ziyonet.uz
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